

GUIDELINES FOR REPLICATION PACKAGES

1. GOAL

The goal of a REPLICATION PACKAGE file is to facilitate the reuse of the code and data, and the verification of the scientific results presented in each article. This ensures transparency, reproducibility, and validation of findings. The package must contain four main ingredients:

(1) ARTICLE: File of the article including all appendices, in PDF.

(2) DATA: Either the raw data, a URL allowing a third party to access the data, or a description of the process for applying to access the data.

(3) CODE: Scripts used for preparing and processing data, running models, and generating results.

(4) README: Plain text, Word, Markdown, or PDF file describing the structure of the package, listing any dependencies (e.g., software, libraries, versions) and explaining how to run the code and reproduce the results.

The structure and contents of the README file requested by **cascad** for verification are inspired by those recommended by the [Social Science Data Editors](#) and by Pérignon et al. (2024). It is also based on actual problems and mistakes we encountered at **cascad** while verifying working papers and conditionally accepted papers at leading academic journals.

2. IDENTIFICATION

Your README file **must** begin with the title of the article, the name of the authors, the authors contact details, the date, and necessary elements to identify the version of the article (e.g., DOI, full reference of the article).

3. DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT

Your README file **must** contain a description of the location and accessibility of the data used in the article. This Data Availability Statement will list all the datasets used in the article, their source and creation date, as well as their location and accessibility. Your description should be clear enough so that even an uninformed user can access them:

- If the datasets are public, simply include the raw data in the package or provide a download link or a DOI to the repository.
- If accessing the data requires an application procedure, indicate where to apply, and, when possible, an estimate of the monetary and time cost of the application process.
- If you generated the data used in a study, you must specify if a license is provided along with it.

Examples (displayed in blue): Here are some examples of Data Availability Statement taken from the [Social Science Data Editors readme template](#) and from readme files we received as part of actual verification requests:

Example of raw data directly included in the package: The data used in the paper are obtained from the Federal Reserve:

- Real GDP, billions of chained 2012 dollars, seasonally adjusted annual rate, 1966-2018 (U.S. Bureau of Economic Analysis)
- Civilian non-institutional population, thousands, 16 years and above, 1966-2018 (U.S. Bureau of Economic Analysis)

The raw data can be found in the usdata.xlsx file in the Data folder.

Example for publicly available data: The [DATA TYPE] data used to support the findings of this study have been deposited in the [NAME] repository ([DOI or OTHER PERSISTENT IDENTIFIER]).

Example for public-use data with required registration: The paper uses IPUMS Terra data. IPUMS-Terra does not allow for redistribution, except for the purpose of replication archives. Permissions as per <https://terra.ipums.org/citation> have been obtained and are documented within the "data/IPUMS-terra" folder.

Example for restricted-access data: The data for this project are confidential but may be obtained with Data Use Agreements with the Massachusetts Department of Elementary and Secondary Education (DESE). Researchers interested in access to the data may contact [NAME] at [EMAIL], also see www.doe.mass.edu/research/contact.html. It can take some months to negotiate data use agreements and gain access to the data. The author will assist with any reasonable replication attempts.

Example for confidential Census Bureau data: All the results in the paper use confidential microdata from the U.S. Census Bureau. To gain access to the Census microdata, follow the directions here on how to write a proposal for access to the data via a Federal Statistical Research Data Center: <https://www.census.gov/ces/rcresearch/howtoapply.html>. You must request the following datasets in your proposal: Longitudinal Business Database (LBD), 2002 and 2007, and Foreign Trade Database – Import (IMP), 2002 and 2007.

Example for confidential French Customs data: The datasets used for this study are confidential but can be accessed through the Centre d'Accès Sécurisé aux Données (CASD):
DOU NC8: Importations et exportations avec les pays extra-Union européenne en nomenclature de produits NC8 <https://www.casd.eu/source/importations-et-exportations-avec-les-pays-extra-union-europeenne-en-nomenclature-de-produits-nc8/>
Researchers wishing to get access should contact the CASD at <https://www.casd.eu/en/contacts-title> and ask for them. Once they have obtained clearance from the Statistical Confidentiality Committee, they will have to take part in an enrolment session after which they will receive a fingerprint-encrypted chip card and a "SD Box". This will allow them to access the data in a secure environment.

In addition, the README file **must** list the file(s) that correspond to each data source as well as their format and location in the package, so that the replicator can check whether a raw dataset is missing or not. We recommend using a Table to summarize all this information (see example below).

Examples from the [Social Science Data Editors readme template](#):

Data File	Source	Provided
data/raw/Cepi1/cepi1.dta	CEPII	Yes
data/raw/Classifications/serv_nat_concordance_MEC.xls	Berlingieri and Pisch (2024)	Yes
data/raw/Classifications/table_NAF-NAF2.xls	INSEE	Yes
data/raw/Comtrade/Comtrade Country Code and ISO list.xls	UN Comtrade	Yes
data/raw/Comtrade/dollar_euro_CPI.dta	IMF-IFS	Yes
data/raw/CouCharacteristics/countrydata.dta	Penn World Tables	Yes
data/raw/CouCharacteristics/EPU_All_Country_Data.xlsx	WB WGI	Yes
data/raw/CreditConstraint/tang_1sic4_ussonly.dta	Baker et al. (2016)	Yes
data/raw/ProdCharacteristics/bundleability1tb.dta	Kroszner et al. (2007)	Yes
\$folder_trans_data/vintage_1995_2016/vintage.*year*.dta	DGDDI	No
\$folder_trans_data/flux1_2011_2017/flux1.*year*.dta	DGDDI	No
\$folder_trans_data/flux2_2011_2017/flux2.*year*.dta	DGDDI	No

4. COMPUTATIONAL REQUIREMENTS

Your README file **must** indicate:

- The software requirements to run the code: that is, all software/programming languages and all packages used by the authors, as well as their respective versions.
- The computing hardware specifications (Operating System, CPU, GPU, memory, disk space). When applicable, you need to specify whether the code runs on the CPU or the GPU.
- The estimated runtime on your machine(s), expressed in appropriate units (e.g. minutes, hours, days).

Note: Even if we do not have the same equipment as the authors, this information provides an estimate of the required hardware and helps us allocate our resources more efficiently.

Examples: Here are some examples of **software requirements descriptions** from the [Social Science Data Editors readme template](#):

Example 1:

Stata (code was last run with version 15)

- estout (as of 2023-02-12)
- egenmore (as of 2019-01-24)
- reghdfe (provided)
- the program "1_Master.do" will install all dependencies locally.

Python 3.6.4

- pandas 0.24.2
- numpy 1.16.4
- the file "requirements.txt" lists these dependencies, please run "pip install -r requirements.txt" as the first step.

Matlab (code was run with Matlab Release 2018a)

Example 2: We explicitly use the following packages in the analysis files:

- Stata/MP 17.0: estout, ivreg2, asdoc (2.3.9.5), and sxpose.
- Python 3.10: openpyxl (3.1.5), pandas (2.2.3), collections, math, numpy (2.1.3), and time.
- MATLAB 9.13: Econometrics Toolbox (6.1), Statistics and Machine Learning Toolbox (12.4), and Optimization Toolbox (9.4).
- R 4.4.0: ggplot2 (3.5.1), readxl (1.4.3), tidyr (1.3.1), tidyverse (2.0.0), writexl (1.5.1), stringr (1.5.1), NLP (0.3.2), ggpubr (0.6.0), reshape2 (1.4.4), patchwork (1.2.0), and haven (2.5.4).

Example 3: Portions of the code use bash scripting, which may require Linux, while others use Powershell scripting, which may require Windows 10 or higher.

Note: Most programming languages and software provide options to export all the dependencies used for your study. For instance:

Language or Software	Command
<i>Stata</i>	<i>ado dir</i>
<i>Python</i>	<i>pip freeze > requirements.txt</i>
<i>Python (anaconda distribution)</i>	<i>conda env export > environment.yml (This file can then be imported by the replicator to use the same environment as the authors)</i>
<i>R</i>	<i>writeLines() or renv::snapshot()</i>
<i>MATLAB</i>	<i>matlab.addons.installed</i>

Most of those commands, however, will list all the dependencies installed on your machine, not just those used by your code.

Examples of descriptions for memory and computer-time requirements, from the [Social Science Data Editors](#) and README files received by cascadi:

- *The scripts were executed on an HP Elite Mini 800 G9 Desktop PC with a 12th Gen Intel(R) Core(TM) i7-1255U processor and 32GB of RAM. With this equipment, the scripts take, in total, about 20 minutes to execute.*
- *The code was last run on a 4-core Intel-based laptop with MacOS version 10.14.4.*
- *Portions of the code were last run on a 32-core Intel server with 1024 GB of RAM, 12 TB of fast local storage. Computation took 30 days.*
- *The parameter estimates reported in the figures and tables come from a Windows desktop version that takes about 5 hours for each [...] model specification. Due to the computational complexity [...], we made use of a computing cluster with a SLURM job scheduler. There are 8 Matlab bootstrap programs [...]. These bootstrap computations were submitted in parallel (i.e. all at once as separate programs) and each took on average 6 days when running on 4 cores.*

5. CODE DESCRIPTION AND INSTRUCTIONS TO REPLICATOR

Your README file **must**:

- List all the scripts used in the study, along with a brief overview of their purpose.
- Contain instructions that allow the replicator to reproduce your results: which scripts must be run, and in which order? Does the replicator need to edit some lines of codes (for example, the ones which set up the folders), and if so, which ones?
- List all the sources of controlled randomness (random seeds), if there are any.

Examples from actual README files:

Example for code description: Folder “Forecasts_M_CarpeDiem” contains monthly forecasts with subfolders:

- “Nowcasts\nowcasts.do” Nowcasts real-time vintages.
- “MIDAS\MIDAS.do” Runs monthly MIDAS forecasts.
- “VAR\VAR.do” Runs monthly VAR forecasts.
- “Graphs\Graphs.do” Produces graphs of monthly data.
- “Graphs\Summarize.do” Produces summary statistics of monthly data.

Example for instructions: The scripts are run in Stata, Python, MATLAB, and R. Roughly, Stata is used to import and clean data, Python is used to construct the density forecast performance measures, MATLAB is used to conduct the statistical tests presented in Tables 1 and 2 [...] and R is used to produce the paper’s figures. [...] x00a_Main.do, x00b_Main.R, and x00c_Main.m run everything in batch, so these are the main executables (x00a_Main.do runs the Python scripts). Start with x00a_Main.do, then run x00b_Main.R, and finish with x00c_Main.m. These main scripts give short descriptions of the other scripts they execute as well as any file paths in these scripts that need to be changed. Please set your working directories and file paths accordingly. Every script also contains a short description of its role at the top of its respective file, including any information pertaining to the generation of a figure or table.

If possible, we **recommend** using one or a few Masterfiles, which will call all the other scripts in order and simplify the verification procedure. In the example above, the code relies on three Masterfiles, one for each section.

We also **recommend** specifying any discrepancies a replicator might encounter, particularly if your code incorporates statistical methods that introduce some level of randomness.

Example from another README file received by cascadi: Even though the Bayesian estimation results are based on two chains of 1,200,000 draws each, there is some probability that the distribution of the posteriors draws varies slightly from one replication to the other. As a result, a replicator should expect minor discrepancies, in the order of 1 to 2 decimal digits, in the estimates provided in Tables 3, 4, and 5 in the manuscript; as well as Table 2 and Figure 7 in the Online Appendix.

6. RESULTS

Regarding the results:

- The code **must** generate all the tables and figures automatically.
- We will not undertake the verification procedure if some of the tables or figures have to be manually reconstructed from results displayed in the software console.

Note: This is the main constraint we impose on your code. We believe this is not only useful for the replicator but for the authors too. Our own experience at **cascad** shows that manually reporting results in the tables is a major source of typos and errors.

- The files used to save tables and figures **must** have a common format: for example, a table can be saved to a LaTeX file, a CSV dataset, an Excel spreadsheet, a Word file or even a TXT or an image. As for a Figure, it can be saved as a JPEG, PNG, EPS or TIF file. We also accept any software-related format: for instance, `.mat` or `.fig` for Matlab tables and Figures, respectively.
- Their names **must** be self-explanatory. For example, if your code is supposed to generate Table 2: Summary Statistics, the file it generates should be named `table2` or `summary_statistics`. In case a Table or Figure is made from several smaller items (e.g., Figure 3 combines six graphs, or Table 4 contains two unrelated panels), we accept one output file per item, but they must be named accordingly: *fig3a*, *table4_panelb*, etc.

We **recommend** you save the results in `./figures` and `./tables` directories.

We also **recommend** you provide a mapping in your readme file, which also links every item (Table or Figure) to the script that computes it.

We provide below an example from a README file we received as part of a verification request:

Figure/Table #	Program	Line Number	Output File	Note
Table 1	1-Master.do	212	Table1.tex	Confidential data
Table 2	1-Master.do	419	Table2.tex	Confidential data
Table 3	1-Master.do	422	Table3.tex	Confidential data
Figure 1	1-Master.do	485	Figure 1.png	Confidential data
Figure 2	- (no data)	-	-	Source: the authors
Figure 3	Figure 3.do	53	Figure 3.png	Source: WTO TISMOS

We also **recommend** providing a codebook in which all variables that are used in the article must be well-described (variable/column labels, value labels, summary statistics). This is especially useful when the variables are not self-explanatory and can help us pinpoint where an issue occurred. If such description already exists within your article, you can point to it instead (e.g., “For summary statistics of variables, see Table 1 in the paper”).

7. FURTHER RECOMMENDATIONS

We **recommend** the following: Your code should contain as many comments as possible, so that any other user can understand it. The readme is not a substitute for such comments.

If possible, we recommend you provide all the intermediary files your code generated. If there is an issue with the code, this can help the replicator backtrace it more easily.

If some datasets cannot be shared at all, you can provide a synthetic dataset instead, to demonstrate that the code does run and generate outputs for all Figures and Tables. When providing a synthetic dataset, please also provide the results you obtained with this alternative dataset.

8. REFERENCES

Pérignon, C., O. Akmansoy, C. Hurlin, A. Menkveld, Dreber, A., Holzmeister, F., Huber, J., Johannesson, M., Kirchler, M., Razen, M., & Weitzel U. (2024). Computational reproducibility in finance: Evidence from 1,000 tests. *Review of Financial Studies*, 37 (11), 3558-3593.

Lars Vilhuber, Connolly, M., Koren, M., Llull, J., & Morrow, P. (2022). A template README for social science replication packages (v1.1). Social Science Data Editors. Available at https://social-science-data-editors.github.io/template_README/.

Social Science Data Editors (2025). "Requested Information for Data". *Data and Code Guidance by Data Editors*. Accessed at https://social-science-data-editors.github.io/guidance/Requested_information_data.html on 2025-02-07.

9. COMPLIANCE CHECKLIST

Before submitting your replication package, fill in the tables below to verify that all requested items and information are provided, and add any additional details to facilitate reproducibility.

Required items or information	Description	Provided? (Yes/No)	Comments
1. Article	Provide a copy of the article.		
2. Code	Provide all the code or a link to a repository.		
3. Data	Provide all the data that you can share.		
4. Readme	Provide a readme file.		
4.1. Data Availability Statement	List all the data sources and how to access them.		
4.2. List of all datasets	List all the data files.		
4.3. Computational requirements	List the Software/languages, OS, CPU, GPU, RAM, disk space, and CPU time.		
4.4. Code description	List all the scripts and seeds along with instructions.		
4.5. Result files	Save the results to external files.		